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Chang Xin
Fudan University

Yang Yini
Fudan University

Yu Yao
Fudan University

Xiong Jianxue
Fudan University

Mei-Sen Shi
Criminal Justice College of China University of Political Science and Law

See next page for additional authors

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Authors

Chang Xin, Yang Yini, Yu Yao, Xiong Jianxue, Mei-Sen Shi, and Wen Shaoqing

Comparative Analysis of Y Chromosome Data from Xinjiang and Ningxia Hui Populations with Hui Population Nationwide

Chang Xin^{1,2#}, Yang Yini^{1,2#}, Yu Yao³, Xiong Jianxue^{1,2}, Mei-Sen Shi^{5*}, Wen Shaoqing^{1,2,4,6*}

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1. Department of Cultural Heritage and Museology, Fudan University, Shanghai, China, 200433
 2. Institute of Archaeological Science, Fudan University, 200433 Shanghai, China
 3. Fudan University Department of History, Fudan University, Shanghai, China, 200433
 4. Ministry of education (MOE) Laboratory for National Development and Intelligent Governance, Fudan University, Shanghai, China, 200433
 5. Criminal Justice College of China University of Political Science and Law, Beijing 100088, China
 6. Center for the Belt and Road Archaeology and Ancient Civilizations, Shanghai 200433, China

These authors contributed equally to this work.

* Corresponding author:

E-mail: shimeisen2000@163.com; wenshaoqing@fudan.edu.cn

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The Hui population, one of China's ethnic minorities, is dispersed throughout the country and has a history of assimilation with indigenous East Asians. Previous studies have primarily focused on Hui populations in specific regions, lacking comprehensive comparative analyses. In this study, we analyzed 338 unrelated male individuals from Hui populations in Altay, Xinjiang, and Haiyuan or Tongxin, Ningxia, using 108 Y-chromosomal single nucleotide polymorphisms (Y-SNPs) and 24 Y-chromosomal short tandem repeats (Y-STRs). We compared our findings with data from 749 published individuals from Hui populations in 11 provinces and 997 published Eurasian populations. Our analysis revealed that the national Hui population can be categorized into three groups: Hui_Northwestern, Hui_Northern, and Hui_Southern, supported by AMOVA and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). In Altay, Xinjiang, and Haiyuan or Tongxin, Ningxia, the most prevalent Y-haplogroups in East Asian

populations accounted for 53.8% and 59.1%, respectively, while common haplogroups in West Eurasian populations accounted for 46.2% and 40.9%, respectively. This suggests a mixed paternal origin from both East Asian and Eurasian populations in both study regions. High frequencies of haplogroups R1a1a1b2-Z93 and J-M304 were observed in the Hui populations studied, with the network of Haplogroup J-M304 indicating a unique cluster within the western Asian sub-haplogroup J2a-M410. The most recent common ancestor for this cluster was estimated to be approximately 1341.9 years ago. Additionally, the network of haplogroup R1a1a1b2-Z93 revealed similarities between northwestern Hui populations and Iranian/Turkic-speaking populations. Our study provides insight into the complexity of Hui populations on a national scale and sheds light on potential events and ancestral origins related to the formation of the Hui population.

The Hui people, the second largest ethnic group in China, are widely dispersed throughout the country. Historical records trace their origins back to the Tang Dynasty, when Arab and Persian Muslim immigrants came to China for trade and warfare (Qiu 1996). The Hui identity took shape during the Yuan and Ming dynasties as the Mongol empire expanded westward, bringing a large number of Muslims from Central Asia to settle in China. They were designated as “Hui” to distinguish them from other ethnic groups. Despite practicing Islam as their religion, the Hui people also share language and culture with the Han majority.

Throughout its history, the Hui people have been known to engage in a process of interaction and assimilation with the Han people as they integrated into China. Previous genetic studies on Hui populations in northwest China have confirmed this close relationship. Various genetic markers, including Indel loci (Xie et al. 2018; Zhou et al. 2020; Zou et al. 2020), AISNP (Chen et al. 2021; Jin et al. 2020), Amelogenin (Chen et al. 2021), A-STRs (Chen et al. 2021), Y-STRs (Chen et al. 2021; Li et al. 2020; Zhu et al. 2014), X-STRs (Chen et al. 2021), IISNP (Chen et al. 2021), and PISNPs (Chen et al. 2021), have been utilized to study Hui populations in Xinjiang, Ningxia, and Gansu provinces, showing that the Hui population has an ancestral component of East Asian origin and close genetic affinities with East Asian populations. Current research on the Hui people primarily focus on northwest China, particularly regions along the Silk Road that have historically been important hubs for communication between China and the Western world. Genome-wide studies of Hui

populations in Ningxia (Ma et al. 2021) have revealed a Western ancestry component (10%) that can be traced back to historical events of population fusion during the Tang Dynasty and Ming Dynasty. Furthermore, investigations of Hui populations in other regions of China, such as Yunnan Province have shown a significant genetic similarity with surrounding ethnic minorities like the Yi, Bai, and Naji, indicating strong gene flow among populations within the same geographical area (Zhang et al. 2022).

There is a lack of comprehensive research articles on the Hui ethnic group across China. Research conducted by Xie (Xie et al. 2019) and Wang (Wang, Lu et al. 2019) has shown that the Hui people share a strong genetic correlation with East Asians, with 70% of their genetic origins tracing back to East Asia and 30% to various regions in western Eurasia. This suggests that the origin and development of the Hui group is linked to the assimilation of indigenous populations in East Asia, as well as significant historical migration events. There is a lack of comprehensive research articles on the Hui ethnic group across China. Variations within the Hui population are evident across different regions, yet previous studies have mainly focused on specific regional populations, neglecting comparative research on genetic structures among diverse regions. Therefore, in this study, we focused on two less studied groups within the Hui population in northwest China: the Altay Hui in Xinjiang and the Haiyuan/Tongxin Hui in Ningxia. Specifically, our study included 338 individuals from Altay Xinjiang and Haiyuan or Tongxin Ningxia, analyzed using a comprehensive set of Y chromosome markers consisting of 108 SNPs and 24 STRs. Additionally, we examined the paternal genetic structure of the entire Hui group using data from 749 individuals across 11 provinces. Through this study, we aim to provide valuable insights into the genetic diversity of the Hui ethnic group in China.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Samples

We collected blood samples of unrelated male individuals of Hui from Altay Xinjiang (N=223) and Haiyuan and Tongxin in Ningxia (N=115). Prior to participation, to ensure transparency and understanding among potential study participants, we advertised and explained the research study through random visits in the residential areas of the Hui people. We verbally described the project to them, ensuring they comprehended the purpose and requirements. Those who expressed interest in supporting the research were then asked to provide informed consent by signing a document. Upon consenting, they became official study participants and provided bloodstain samples for data collection. The study underwent ethical review by the Ethics Committee of the School of Life Sciences at Fudan University on February 28, 2014. Following submission of the necessary ethics approval materials, the Ethics Committee approved the study with the number 14012. DNA samples were extracted using the QIAamp DNA Blood Mini Kit (QIAGEN, Germany), and hierarchical genotyping was performed using the SNaPshot method with the ABI SNaPshot Multiplex Kit.

There were 108 Y-SNP markers and 24 STR loci were analyzed in all 338 DNA samples, following methods described in previous studies (Wen et al. 2017). Y haplogroups were classified according to the ISOGG Y-DNA Haplogroup Tree 2019 (Version: 15.73; Date: 11 July 2020). The 24 analyzed Y-STR loci data had been previously reported (Li et al. 2020; Mei et al. 2016).

A total of 1087 male samples from 11 provinces were included in the study (see Supplementary Table 1, Fig.1). Except the new reported samples, the remaining 749 samples were sourced from existing literature (Gansu N=167(Xie et al. 2019); Xinjiang N=173, Ningxia N=56, Tianjin N=65, Shandong N=53, Henan N=66, Anhui N=23, Jiangsu N=59, Yunnan N=44, Guangxi N=23, Fujian N=20(Wang, Lu et al. 2019)).

2.2 Statistical analysis

The Y-chromosome haplogroup frequencies were determined through counting, while

allele frequencies and forensic parameters such as expected heterozygosity (Hexp), discrimination power (DP), and polymorphism information content (PIC) were calculated using STRAF (STR Analysis for Forensics, <http://cmpg.unibe.ch/shiny/STRAF/>) (Gouy and Zieger 2017). To ensure consistency with reference data, the allele frequencies and forensic parameters were based on analysis of 17 STR markers. Analysis of Molecular Variance (AMOVA) was conducted using Arlequin software to identify population differentiation (Excoffier et al. 1992). The Hui samples were compared to other Sino-Tibetan, Altaic, and Central Asian populations, as well as surrounding areas, utilizing data from previous studies at a similar level of haplogroup resolution. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed using R studio, and a heatmap was generated using TBtools (v1.098726) based on Rst(Chen, Chen et al. 2020). Y-chromosomal STR data for haplogroups J-M304 and R1a-Z93 were analyzed using NETWORK v10.2.0.0 (<https://www.fluxus-engineering.com/>). DYS389II was calculated by subtracting the DYS389I allele size for these analyses. The time to the most recent common ancestor (TMRCA) of each distinct cluster (DC) was determined using the average squared distance (ASD) estimator, with a generation time of 25 years used to estimate time in years (Wang and Li 2015; Wang et al. 2014; Wen et al. 2017).

3. Results

Y chromosome haplogroups of 338 Hui males from Altai Xinjiang and Ningxia were determined according to the ISOGG's Y-DNA Haplogroup Tree 2019 (Supplementary Table 1). The allele frequency distributions and forensic parameters are listed in Supplementary Table 3. The Hexp ranged from 0.4499 at DYS391 locus to 0.8987 at DYS385b locus while the DP ranged from 0.4495 at DYS391 locus to 0.8979 at DYS385b locus. PIC of all selected loci ranged from 0.3869 at DYS391 to 0.8889 at DYS385b. The allele frequencies are listed in Supplementary Table 3. The most polymorphic loci in Hui populations are highly discriminating, indicating that this set of loci will be useful for forensic identification.

According to the Y-DNA Haplogroup Tree 2019 lineage provided by ISOGG, a comparison was made between the Y-haplogroup distribution of the Altai Hui people in Xinjiang and the Hui people in Ningxia with that of the Hui population in other provinces across China (Fig.1). The study included a total of 1087 individuals from various Hui ethnic groups in Gansu, Tianjin, Shandong, Henan, Anhui, Jiangsu, Yunnan, Guangxi and Fujian. We conducted a simplified phylogenetic tree (Fig.2) to illustrate the haplogroup distribution between these groups. The most prevalent haplogroups among the Altai Hui population in Xinjiang were R1a1a1b2-Z93 (14.35%) and J-M304 (13.45%), while for Haiyuan and Tongxin Hui populations in Ningxia it was J-M304 (12.17%) and R1a1a1b2-Z93 (10.43%).

Haplogroup R1a1a1b2-Z93 is highly prevalent in South Asia (25%) (Karafet et al. 2016) and Central Asia (18%) (Karafet et al. 2016), as well as in Kyrgyzstan (6%) (Underhill et al. 2015) and all Iranian populations (1–8%) (Underhill et al. 2015). It is also found in Malaysian Indians, Hungarian Roma, Uzbeks, and Mongolians (Pamjav et al. 2012). Haplogroup J is associated with the Neolithic demic diffusion linked to the spread of agriculture (Di Giacomo et al. 2004; Semino et al. 1996). J-M304 can be divided into two sub-haplogroups, J1-M267 and J2-M172 (Cinnioglu et al. 2004), which are distributed differently in the Near East, North Africa, and Europe (Semino et al. 2004). Haplogroup J1-M267 is common in the Near East (Chiaroni et al. 2010), while J2-M172 is believed to have spread from the Levant and Anatolia to southeastern Europe (Cinnioglu et al. 2004). Our study aims to determine which sub-haplogroup our Hui samples belong to through Network analysis. Additionally, R1a1a*-M17, M198, and J-M304 are prevalent in Hui from other Chinese provinces such as Gansu, Tianjin, Shandong, and Henan, indicating a genetic connection between the Hui group and populations from Central Asia.

The Altai Hui population in Xinjiang exhibits a variety of haplogroups, including O α -M117 (6.73%), O γ -IMS-JST002611 (6.73%), and O2a2b1a2-F444 (5.38%). Similarly, the Haiyuan and Tongxin Hui populations in Ningxia have frequencies of O γ -IMS-JST002611 (7.83%), O α -M117 (6.09%), and O2a2b1a2-F444 (6.09%). The haplogroup O β -F46 is a downstream lineage of O2a2b1a2-F444.

Haplogroups O γ -IMS-JST002611 (16%), O- α -M117 (11%), and O- β -F46 (3.3%) are believed to have originated from Neolithic farmers in the Yellow River Basin and are prevalent in many East Asian populations, including an estimated 30% of the present Han Chinese population (16% for O α , 11% for O β , and 14% for O γ) (Yan et al. 2014).

Haplogroups G-M201, I-M170 and M258, E-M96, C2b1-F2613, D1a1a1a-N1, N1a1a-M178, N1b-F2930 were also found in Altai, Xinjiang, and Haiyuan and Tongxin Hui populations in Ningxia. Haplogroup G is predominantly found in the Caucasus region, with North Ossetians exhibiting the highest frequency at over 70% (Balanovsky et al. 2011; Yunusbayev et al. 2011), gradually decreasing to 13% in Iran (Regueiro et al. 2006) and further diminishing as it spreads eastward. Frequencies range from 5% to 15% in the Near/Middle East and southern European countries, such as Italy and Greece, with a declining gradient towards the Balkans and northern Europe (Battaglia et al. 2009; Capelli et al. 2007; Gonçalves et al. 2005; King et al. 2008). Haplogroup G, along with J2 clades, has been linked to the expansion of agriculture, particularly in Europe (Rootsi et al. 2012). Haplogroup I is a prevalent component of the European Y-chromosome gene pool (Rootsi et al. 2004), showing a decrease in frequency with increasing longitude, suggesting gene flow from Europe (Cinnioglu et al. 2004). Haplogroup E is present in Africa, Europe, and the Near East (Semino et al. 2004). Haplogroup D1a1a1a-N1, a subgroup of haplogroup D-M174, is primarily found among Tibetans (40.96%) and Japanese (35.71%), with lower or negligible distribution in surrounding regions (Qian et al. 2019). Haplogroups C2b1-F2613, N1a1a-M178, and N1b-F2930 are common in East Asia, Siberia, and Northeast European populations.

To provide a clearer illustration, we analyzed the frequency distribution of haplogroups in Ningxia and Xinjiang Hui populations compared to Hui populations from other provinces, as well as the Han population and other minority ethnic groups (see Fig. 3). We categorized the frequency of each haplogroup (C-M130, D-M174, N-M231, O-M175, and Q-M242 in blue; J-M304, R-M304, and other haplogroups in yellow) based on their distribution. Interestingly, our observations show that from the

paternal perspective, Hui people generally have a higher East Asian genetic component compared to a west Eurasian component, consistent with previous research findings. Furthermore, we noted significant differences in the genetic structure of Hui populations between the Yellow and Yangtze River basins. In northwest China and along the Yellow River, Hui populations have a higher west Eurasian genetic component compared to the local Han population. Conversely, in the Yangtze River basin and southern regions, the percentage of west Eurasian genetic component is lower among Hui populations. Notably, Hui populations in Yunnan stand out from other southern Hui populations due to their migration from central Asia and northwest China with the army during the Yuan to Qing dynasties, which is well-documented in historical records.

To further investigate the structure within Hui groups, an AMOVA analysis was conducted (see Supplementary Table 4). By dividing the samples into geographical subgroups (Hui population from northwest China—NWH, including Xinjiang, Ningxia, and Gansu provinces; Hui population from north China—NH, including Henan, Tianjin, Shandong, and Anhui provinces; and Hui population from south China—SH, including Yunnan, Guangxi, Fujian, and Jiangsu provinces), it was found that among groups, the percentage of variation is 0.59% ($p=0$), within groups the percentage of variation is 0.82% ($p=0$), and within the population is 98.59% ($p=0$).

To explore the relationship between the Hui ethnic group and surrounding populations, we analyzed genetic data from 162 East Asian and European populations alongside the Hui people in China. Through a principal component analysis (PCA) based on Y-SNP, we visually represented the outcomes in a graph showcasing the first two principal components, which collectively explain 31.5% of the variation (Fig.4(a)). Notably, populations with shared language families or ethnic backgrounds tend to cluster together. Chinese individuals are in the top left quadrant, Tibeto-Burman people in the bottom left, Mongolian, Altai, and Uralic populations in the middle, and Indo-European communities on the right. Interestingly, the Hui individuals occupy an intermediate position between Sino-Tibetan and Altai/Indo-

European clusters, with those from southern and eastern China closer to Sino-Tibetan populations, and those from northwest China closer to Altai/Indo-European groups. This suggests genetic variations among regional subgroups of the Hui people in China. However, Hui individuals in Yunnan stand out as their distribution aligns closely with the Northwest Hui population in the PCA. This similarity can be attributed to historical influx of ancestral migration into Yunnan from various regions such as Arabia, Central Asia, West Asia, Central Plains, and Northwest China throughout history (Yang 1994). The genetic affinity between the Northwest Hui population and Altai/Indo-European populations is primarily due to contributions from haplogroups J, R1b1a1b*, R2a, and I (Figure 4(b)).

To explore the intricate relationships between the Hui population and other related groups at an individual level, we conducted a detailed analysis of major lineages within Hui samples using reduced median networks. Populations were categorized and compared based on haplogroup or language families. We found that the Haplogroup J-M304 is more prevalent in the Hui population, leading us to prioritize its examination. The distribution of sub haplogroups J1 and J2 within haplogroup J-M304 varies among the Hui population, prompting us to construct a simplified median network to visualize this distribution. Our analysis revealed that individuals in the Hui group are predominantly found within the J2 haplogroup. Further investigation into the J2* lineage showed a distinct genetic structure within the Hui population, forming a unique cluster with multiple recent expansions. By selecting lineages with fewer than five mutations, we identified a lineage containing Hui samples from various regions in China, as well as Gansu Yugur and Mongolian samples for comparison. Using the ASD methodology, we determined that these samples share a most recent common ancestor approximately 1341.9 years ago.

We have also constructed a reduced median network of haplogroup R1a1a1b2-Z93, which includes a significant number of Hui individuals from Ningxia and Xinjiang in our study. Interestingly, this haplogroup was not found in the Hui population in provinces outside of Xinjiang, Ningxia, and Gansu. In the center of Fig.7, Hui individuals from Gansu Province (yellow) and Turkic-speaking individuals

(lilac) are depicted. Haplogroup R1a1a1b2-Z93 spread across Eurasia during the Bronze Age by Indo-European pastoralists and is now present in various Turkic groups. Currently, this haplogroup is most commonly observed in Central/South Asia, with lower frequencies in Europe and the Near East (Pamjav et al. 2012; Underhill et al. 2015). Our network analysis results show that this haplogroup is most prevalent among Iranian-speaking and Turkic-speaking groups, with the Chinese northwest Hui group dispersed among them.

Given the widespread distribution of the various lineages under haplogroup O in East Asia and the limited accuracy of available data, this study chose not to conduct network analysis on these lineages.

Discussion

This study examined the Hui population in the Altai Region of Xinjiang and in the Haiyuan or Tongxin regions of Ningxia as the primary research subjects. The haplogroup composition of these specific Hui populations showed no significant differences.

Our study compared various populations with the Hui population nationwide to analyze their genetic structure and formation history, aiming to identify similarities and differences. Regional variations in the genetic structure of the Hui population in China were observed, and subsequent AMOVA analysis confirmed that the Hui population can be categorized into three distinct regional groups: Hui_Northwestern, Hui_Northern, and Hui_Southern. These variations are a result of complex interactions between different regions of China and surrounding populations throughout history, involving genetic admixture and cultural assimilation. Previous research has indicated that the Hui population has been mainly influenced by cultural assimilation from both paternal and maternal perspectives. Indigenous East Asian ancestry contributes to 70% of the paternal ancestry of the Hui population (Wang, Lu et al. 2019), with the Hui group showing the smallest genetic divergences (pairwise F_{st} values) with Han populations among 99 worldwide populations based on

mitochondrial haplogroups (Chen, Li et al. 2020). Additionally, the Western Eurasian components of the Hui population are a result of genetic admixture between the local population and surrounding populations in earlier periods, leading to differences in paternal genetic structure between regions. From a genetic lineage perspective, there is a decline in Western Eurasian components from northwest to southeast along the Silk Road. The Hui ethnic group in Xinjiang region has the highest Western Eurasian components due to its proximity to Muslim countries in Central Asia and high population exchanges. The Hui people along the Hexi Corridor and the Silk Road also show a higher Western Eurasian component, likely due to trade. In contrast, Yunnan Hui in the south has a unique history, with a significant number of Central Asian and Arab immigrants during the Yuan Dynasty (Yang 1994). The proportion of Western Eurasian components among Yunnan Hui is different from other regions, indicating a direction of population diffusion. Overall, trade and warfare facilitated population movements, but cultural assimilation played a crucial role in the formation of the Hui population, with varying proportions of Western Eurasian components across regions indicating a diffusion pattern along the Silk Road.

To explore the relationship between the Hui people and the surrounding population, we conducted a lineage analysis. Our research identified the J2a-M410 lineage as the predominant male lineage among the Hui individuals, with origins in Western Asia. This haplogroup has been found in ancient DNA samples from various regions including Irian(Lazaridis et al. 2016), Turkmenistan(de Barros Damgaard et al. 2018; Narasimhan et al. 2019), Kazakhstan(de Barros Damgaard et al. 2018; Gneccchi-Ruscione et al. 2021; Narasimhan et al. 2019), Uzbekistan(Narasimhan et al. 2019), Pakistan(Narasimhan et al. 2019), Kyrgyzstan(Gneccchi-Ruscione et al. 2021), Turkey(de Barros Damgaard et al. 2018; Mathieson et al. 2015; Skourtanioti et al. 2020), and other Central and Western Asian areas, as well as in European countries like Italy(Antonio et al. 2019; Fernandes et al. 2020), Spain(Olalde et al. 2019), and Russia(Wang, Reinhold et al. 2019). Our network analysis revealed that the Hui population forms a distinct branch within the J2a lineage, dating back to the Sui and Tang Dynasties. We also found genetic connections of Hui with other local ethnic

groups such as the Yugur and Mongolian.

Furthermore, our study of the R1a1a1b2-Z93 lineage showed that the origins of the Hui people are complex, with some influences from Iranian and Turkic groups. The Persian language group, represented mainly by Persians from Persia along the Silk Road, might played a significant role in the formation of the Hui ethnicity. Historical records from the Han Dynasty document interactions between China and Persia, including diplomatic missions and trade exchanges (Qiu 1996). Turkic speakers, who have historical ties to the Central Plains despite their nomadic lifestyle, also contributed to the genetic makeup of the Hui population. Our analysis indicated that the R1a1a1b2-Z93 lineage is prevalent among Hui individuals in northwestern China, also showing closer genetic relationships with Iranians and Turkic populations.

Overall, our findings suggest a complex and multifaceted origin for the Hui people, with influences from various ethnic groups and historical events. Further research is needed to fully understand the formation process of the Hui ethnicity.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

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FIGURES

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.3

Fig.4 (a)

Fig.4 (b)

Fig.5

Fig.6

Fig.7

Figure captions

Fig.1 the geographical location of Hui samples

Fig.2 The phylogenetic relationship of Y-chromosome haplogroups in this study and their haplogroup-based frequencies in the sampled populations. The Last row is the Haplogroup Diversity (HD) calculated by Y-SNP. Haplogroup names are shown along the branches, and marker names are shown to the right, based on ISOGG Y-DNA Haplogroup Tree 2019.

Fig.3 Visualizing the frequency of Y-SNP haplogroups of Chinese Hui population and other ethnic groups, which were divided into two groups, one is the representative haplogroups of East Asian and the other is of Eurasia.

Fig.4 Phylogenetic relationship by PCA with the frequencies of haplogroups.

Fig.4 (a) PC map of the Hui and reference populations based on haplogroup frequencies.

Fig.4 (b) Biplot of the Hui people that shows the haplogroup contribution of the first and second PCs.

Fig.5 Networks of the STR haplotypes associated with haplogroups J-M304 observed in the study sample of Hui population and compared population using data from 15 Y-STR loci (DYS19, DYS389I, DYS389b, DYS390, DYS391, DYS392, DYS393, DYS439, DYS437, DYS438, DYS448, DYS456, DYS458, DYS635, DYS-GATA-H4), setting colors based on haplogroups.

Fig.6 Networks of the STR haplotypes associated with haplogroups J2* observed in the study sample of Hui population and compared population using data from 15 Y-STR loci (DYS19, DYS389I, DYS389b, DYS390, DYS391, DYS392, DYS393, DYS439, DYS437, DYS438, DYS448, DYS456, DYS458, DYS635, DYS-GATA-H4), setting colors based on haplogroups.

Fig.7 Networks of the STR haplotypes associated with haplogroups R1a1a1b2-Z93 observed in the study sample of Hui population and compared population using data from 15 Y-STR loci (DYS19, DYS389I, DYS389b, DYS390, DYS391, DYS392, DYS393, DYS439, DYS437, DYS438, DYS448, DYS456, DYS458, DYS635, DYS-GATA-H4). Circles and colored sectors are proportional to the number of subjects, with the smallest circle and sector equal to 1.

Supporting Information

Table S1. Y chromosome SNP and STR data of Xinjiang & Ningxia Hui and other reference populations. The Y chromosomal SNP information and 24 Y-STRs are provided.

Table S2. Haplogroup Diversity the Xinjiang & Ningxia Hui and other reference populations.

Table S3. The allele distribution frequencies and GD values of Y-STR loci in the Xinjiang & Ningxia Hui.

Table S4. AMOVA analysis of national Hui data

Table S5. Y chromosome haplogroup frequencies in 157 populations included in the PCA plots.

Table S6. Haplotypes for 15 Y-STR loci of all individuals in the network of haplogroup J-M304

Table S7. Haplotypes for 15 Y-STR loci of all individuals in the network of haplogroup J2-M172

Table S8. Haplotypes for 15 Y-STR loci of all individuals in the network of haplogroup

R1a1a1b2-Z93